

DEVELOPMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CREATING HUMOR IN UZBEK CHILDREN'S POETRY

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Abstract. The poetic image, artistic details, and situation that cause laughter, words, and concepts in humorous poems must have a gradual development through the evolution of thinking with the renewal of space and time, object and subject.

Keywords: humor, laughter, comic, psychology, anecdote, theme, plot, idea, symbol, evolution, rhyme, imitation words.

Current Uzbek children's poetry is gradually developing in terms of the peculiarities of different eras, including the traditions of creating a poetic image, the use of artistic details and tools, and the artist's style and skill. After all, children's perception, understanding, and emotional world do not freeze in one place but acquire a colorful principle. Accordingly, in the works dedicated to them, the character of the hero changes, in addition to the theme and plot, the importance of form and content, idea and thought becomes important. Of course, the role of humor and artistic-aesthetic function in children's poetry is no exception. Laughter takes place in the presence of at least two objects, that is, between the subject of laughter and the laugher. Accordingly, the work expressed using images that carry the function of laughter, humorous, comic images, funny situations in the reality of the plot, and certain comic characters in the actions and speech of the characters, is called a humorous work.

Although humor in literature, in general, is primarily based on harmless laughter, it can be said that its social, literary, and aesthetic functions in different periods have been diverse. Let's say, in the 30s of the last century, to expose the flaws in the character of children of junior school age, their dirty behavior without observing hygiene, not treating their teeth on time (G.Gulam's "Nortojining kurak tishi". "Ahmad yomon bola emasku, ammo.. .") or the psychological image of 8-11-year-old students who do not learn subjects at school (poems such as S.Jura's "Cho'ntak", "Mamatning kechirmishlari", "Yolg'onchi", "Qarzdor", "Dum" by Q. Muhammadi) become visible. For example, the hero of Sultan Jura's poem "Qarzdor"(The Debtor) lays his head on the pillow at night because he got low grades at school and is in debt, but he can't close his eyes and remains in thought. He dreams in the middle of the night: he is afraid that someone has blocked his path while he is going somewhere.

Shuddered boy, when he looked closer, it turned out that this was the subject of "Arithmetic"... Sweated and dumbfounded Kadir, thought to get rid of it.

Arithmetic pursues him and Kadir runs away when he accidentally escapes from his grasp. Fleeing, tripping over a stone, and sliding into a large hole, he opens his eyes and realizes that he fell out of bed... Thanks to this dream, he will study well and get rid of his debt with the help of his friends. This humorous poem reflects the poet's positive and funny attitude towards reality. One can only hope that the above defects will be rectified on such a funny plot. For this reason, in the research work on the factors of the appearance of satire and humor in Z.Ahmedova's children's poetry, it is emphasized that the method of making people laugh through mockery is the leading method. The new age and new thinking will certainly change society's attitude to humor. "With humor, people are not mocked angrily, they are not subjected to soul-killing laughter. "Laughter is humor aimed at eliminating defects that do not have a serious negative character, that expose people who have not committed criminal acts, that are easy to heal, and that have not taken deep roots," the sources say. It is an English word that means "polite laughter". According to linguist S.I. Ojegov, the meaning of humor is the ability to see and show something funny, to react to something through comic understanding, the art of turning something into a comical situation, and speech based on humor that provokes laughter. Indeed, expressions of humor in children's poetry perform various literary and aesthetic tasks. G. Joraeva says that it "as an educational tool reveals individuality, cheerfulness, and slyness in the nature of the lyrical hero, makes the work readable, encourages children to get rid of all kinds of vices; avoids being exposed to various defects, cultivates a culture of correct criticism along with a sense of humor," he says. At the same time, it should be noted that the functions of humor in contemporary children's poetry are more significant and comprehensive. It can be said that the object and theme of humor in children's poetry have expanded even more. Although many vices in society - backbiting, gossiping, cheating, treachery, gluttony, laziness - are found among adults, but in this works, they are satirized by the nature of children. The method of exposure in R. Tolipov's poems such as "Bitta yomon"(One bad), "Har kim o'z aybin bilmas"(Everyone does not know his own fault)", "Olifla"(Blowhard), "Qurumsoq"(Beggar), "Tekin ziyofat"(Free party), "Ochofat", (Glutton) "Hasadgo'y"(Envy), "Qizg'anchiq"(Jealous) by Anvar Obidjon creates humor. In the poems of poets such as T.Adashboev, Q. O'taev, A. Obidjon, H. Imomberdiev,

D. Rajabov, A.Akbar, mixed with light humor, the introduction of serious social content began to take the lead.

Thus, in modern children's poetry, the artistic and aesthetic tasks of humor are not to expose and ridicule the misbehavior and character flaws of schoolchildren, children, but to pay more attention to the problems related to the changes in the thinking of society and social development, along with the changes in the mentality of the young generation. It turns into an aesthetic principle, like the growth of legal consciousness, and shows that it created the principle of gradual development.

The present period is important in Uzbek children's poetry, because the comedy, symbolism and artistic tools that form the artistic-aesthetic basis of humor are aimed at educating young people with greatness, self-confidence, intellectually sharp potential, aesthetic taste.

References:

1. Jamilova B.S. and Qahhorova M.Y. Bolalar detective nasrida o'smirlar ruhiyati tasviri// International scientific methodical journal, ISSN 2181-1709(P), 2181-1717(E) , 2020,1. <http://interscience.uz/>
2. Jamilova B. , Qahhorova M. Comparative interpretation of the characters in English and Uzbek novels. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol. 27, Issue 2. – Australia, 2021. DOI: 10.47750/cibg.2021.27.02.169 .
3. O'ZIGA XOS TALQINLARI //Namdu ilmiy axborotnomasi. - 2020. - T. 1. - S. 5,311-319.
4. Jamilova B., Nuriddinova Sh. The spiritual description of adults in uzbek children's prose-the place of literary psychologism. Academicia: An international multidisciplinary research journal. Vol. 11 Issue 1, January. – Indiya, 2021. Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 7.492.
5. Jamilova B. Poetical treatment of conception of time . International scientific and practical conference world Science Proceedings of the conference –Scientific issues of the modernity!. Vol.III. Rost Publishing Dubai, 2015.
6. Rustamova G., Sharofova G. USMON AZIM SHE'RIYATIDA KO'Z BILAN BOG 'LIQ SOMATIK OBRAZLAR DINAMIK POETIKASI //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 43-46.
7. Qobilova A.A. LINGUOPOETIC AND COMMUNICATIVE FEATURES OF HUMOR IN UZBEK CHILDREN'S POETRY. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR) Impact Factor. SJIF 2021 = 7.699

8. Qobilova A.A. Anvar Obidjonning yumoristik she'rlarida an'ana va takomil.
- Buxoro davlat universiteti ilmiy axboroti. 6/2023
9. Qobilova A.A. Boshlang'ich sinflarda umummilliy qadriyatlarni singdirishda Anvar Obidjon ijodining o'рни. "BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIM SIFAT VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH:STRATEGIYA,
10. INNOVATSIYA VA ILG'OR TAJRIBALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI MATERIALLARI. Buxoro: - 2021.

